

MODELING ISOTHERMAL PROCESSES IN DRYING

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Introduction. Plant cells are organised into tissues, resulting in three different environmental compartments at the micro level; intercellular, intracellular and cell wall [1-2]. These are filled with water and/or air in different ratios, resulting in the formation of plant food materials closely related to the structure of the porous medium [3]. Water stored in the intercellular medium is known as free water, whereas intracellular water and firmly bound water can be found in intracellular compartments and cell wall compartments, respectively [1]. Intercellular spaces composed of air and water vapour contribute to the initial porosity of plant-based food materials [4]. This complex cellular organisation of plant-based food materials has complicated the distribution and transport of water. Thus, effective processing/preservation methods for plant-based food products should be chosen carefully, not only considering their high water content, but also taking into account the complex nature of water distribution and porous nature manifested in their heterogeneous cellular level. Structures [1-4].

In this work we investigate consisting of their thermodynamic properties, optimal drying and storage conditions. We analyse the results of kinetics and shrinkage during drying to establish the drying characteristics of common basil in simulations. One of the objectives of this simulation is to better understand the parameters related to drying and to modify the thermal and dynamic behaviour of the modular drying system in order to optimise the drying of common basil in a modular solar dryer.

To determine the sorption and desorption isotherms of common basil, we chose the static gravimetric method. This method is based on the use of saturated solutions of salts maintaining constant relative humidity. The salts

used are KOH, (MgCl₂, 6H₂O), K₂CO₃, NaNO₃, KCl and (BaCl₂, 2H₂O) Table 1. These salts have water activities ranging from 0.05 to 0.9 [5-8].

Two experiments are conducted:

Sorption - the original sample is placed in an oven for 6 hours at 100 °C to lose all free moisture, the product absorbs moisture during the experiment;

Desorption - the original sample was not pretreated, the product loses moisture (using fresh common basil).

We conduct two experiments that will last about 10 days for desorption and 12 days for sorption (we measure to hygroscopic equilibrium).

Table 1. Standard values of water activity (a_w) of six limiting salts used for determination of sorption curves [5-8]

Salt solutions	Water activities, a_w		
	35 °C	45 °C	55 °C
KOH	0,0748	0,0631	0,0586
MgCl ₂ , 6H ₂ O	0,3247	0,3163	0,3067
K ₂ CO ₃	0,4325	0,4242	0,4089
NaNO ₃	0,7283	0,7121	0,6922
KCl	0,8371	0,8247	0,8135
BaCl ₂ , 2H ₂ O	0,8994	0,8924	0,8839

Characteristics related to product moisture include product moisture content and product water activity.

Product water activity. The water contained in a product is more or less available. This availability is quantified by the product water activity, defined for a given temperature as the ratio between the partial pressure of water vapour at the product surface and the saturated air pressure:

$$a_w = \frac{W_{otn.}}{100} = \left(\frac{P_T}{P_{raw.}} \right)_T = \left(\frac{P_p}{P_{raw.}} \right)_T \quad (1)$$

Where, a_w -activity of water; $W_{otn.}$ -relative humidity of air, %; $P_{raw.}$ -partial pressure of saturating water vapour at equilibrium temperature, Pa; P_p -partial pressure of water vapour on product surface, Pa; P_T -partial pressure of water vapour in thermal air, Pa; R -constant of ideal gas, 8,31 J/mol; T -temperature, °C.

Relative humidity varies from 0% to 100% and water activity (a_w) from 0 to 1.

When hygroscopic equilibrium is reached, we have:

$$a_w = \frac{M}{100} \quad (2)$$

Where, a_w -water activity; M -hygroscopic equilibrium, %.

Hygroscopic equilibrium: relative humidity of the air in equilibrium with the product (%).

If you want to preserve a dried product, you need to know the moisture content of the product, which is related to its stability. In the hygroscopic domain, there is a macroscopic relationship between the equilibrium moisture content of the product and the relative humidity of the environment. Thus, knowing the adequate equilibrium moisture content of a product leads to the fact that the value of the ambient relative humidity must be taken into account for its proper preservation. The relationship relating the moisture content to the ambient relative humidity at a given temperature is called the sorption isotherm.

We weigh the samples contained in the jars every 48 hours until thermodynamic equilibrium is reached. In this way, we calculate the equilibrium moisture content for each relative humidity. It should be noted that mould forms on the higher moisture content samples, KCl and BaCl₂. The equilibrium measurement should not account for these foreign bodies.

Determination of sorption isotherms requires knowledge of three quantities: temperature, relative humidity and moisture content. Temperature is measured using a precision thermometer ± 0.1 °C. For the salts used, the relative humidity has an error of 0.5 to 1.5 per cent. Finally, a scale to weigh each sample is accurate to ± 0.001 g.

We obtained three desorption isotherms and three sorption isotherms. They have a type II sigmoidal shape, similar to those commonly found in agricultural products, aromatic and medicinal plants.

The sorption and desorption isotherms are equilibrium curves that, at constant temperature, relate the moisture content of a product to its water activity (which is equal to the ambient relative humidity at hygroscopic equilibrium).

The phenomena of sorption and desorption involve a certain number of physical phenomena: the nature and hygroscopic state of the product, the nature of the bonds between water molecules and the solid matrix of the product.

Empirical modelling of sorption isotherms. Many expressions have been proposed for modelling sorption isotherms. Some of them are based on a theoretical model of sorption (GAB model) and others are empirical in nature. The disadvantage of all these expressions is that they are not applicable over the whole range of relative humidity. In Table 2 we present the most commonly used models.

Table 2. Mathematical smoothing models used for modelling the sorption isotherms of common basil [5]

Modelles	Equation
Henderson	$1 - a_w = \exp.[(A + B)W_{paB.}^C]$
Chung-Pfost	$a_w = \text{exs.} \left[\frac{A}{B} \text{exs.}(-CW_{raw.}) \right]$
Oswin	$W_{raw.} = (A + B) \left[\frac{a_w}{1 - a_w} \right]^C$
Halsey	$a_w = \text{exs.} \left[\frac{-\text{exs.} (A + B)}{C_{raw.}^C} \right]$
GAB (Guggenheim-Anderson-de Boer)	$W_{raw.} = \frac{ABCa_w}{[1 - Ba_w][1 - Ba_w + BCa_w]}$

Where, A, B, C are model coefficients; $W_{raw.}$ -equal water content, %; C and B-constants.

Regression models are compared based on their correlation coefficients R^2 , mean relative error and mean systematic product error [7, 8]. The highest value of R^2 , the lowest values of relative mean error and mean systematic error are the criteria justifying the choice of the most appropriate model to describe the sorption isotherms.

These statistical parameters are calculated as follows:

$$C = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{W_{exs.} - W_{model.}}{W_{exs.}} \right| \quad (3)$$

$$Y = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{i,model.}^* - \bar{X}_{i,exs.}^*)}{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{i,exs.}^* - \bar{X}_{i,exs.}^*)} \quad (4)$$

Where, Y-relative mean error; C-mean systematic error; $W_{exs.}$ -experimental equilibrium moisture content; $W_{model.}$ -modelling equilibrium moisture content; N-number of experimental points; n-number of coefficients.

The study of sorption isotherms allows us to know the optimum equilibrium relative humidity for product preservation. All experimental points are combined in the graph. Then we can model the sorption isotherm by a 3rd degree function. The part close to horizontal corresponds to the zone of best product stability.

The net isosteric heat of sorption is nothing but the determinant of the curve representing $\ln(a_w)$ as a function of $\left(\frac{1}{T}\right)$ for constant product content. Differential entropy, in turn, represents the intersection of the curve with the ordinate axis to the nearest R.

It should be noted that the change in sorption entropy depending on the equilibrium moisture content is similar to the change in isosteric heat of sorption. This property gives rise to the compensation theory.

Fig. 1. Hysteresis between sorption and desorption isotherms of common basil at 45 °C

The obtained curves show that at the same water activity, the equilibrium water content increases with decreasing temperature.

The hysteresis phenomenon is observed in the sorption-desorption isotherms of common basil at 45 °C (Fig. 1). A type II hysteresis phenomenon is observed in common basil.

Indeed, the sorption and desorption curves of these products show that at the same value of water activity, the desorption moisture content is greater than the sorption moisture content. At the same constant relative humidity, the desorption moisture content is higher than the sorption moisture content. Here this difference increases with increasing relative humidity. This characteristic is noticeable to some extent in all aromatic and medicinal plants. Various hypotheses have been put forward to explain the phenomenon of hysteresis. One of them is the sponge analogy. In fact, when you try to completely wet a sponge, it must be crushed to free the pores from the air they trap. This is the case with common basil. When the pores no longer contain water, sorption prevents all of the original water from being recovered (because it traps air in the pores).

Conclusions. The study of sorption isotherms allows us to know the optimum equilibrium relative humidity to preserve the product, as well as the

equilibrium moisture content to be reached at the end of drying. All experimental points are collected on one graph, then we can model the sorption isotherm by a polynomial of the 3rd degree of water activity (a_w). The part close to horizontal corresponds to the zone of best product stability.

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